

Rural Women's Symbolic Adoption of Energy Conservation Equipment

Meenu¹ and Yashpal Yadav²

Department of Resource Management and Consumer Science, I.C. College of Community Science

Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana¹

Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Technology and Engineering Maharana Pratap

University of Agriculture & Technology, Udaipur, Rajasthan²

Energy-efficient technologies such as improved cook stoves, solar lights and low-consumption appliances play a crucial role in reducing energy use and promoting sustainable living in rural areas. Symbolic adoption refers to the initial willingness and intent to adopt such technologies. Rural women, who bear significant domestic and economic burdens, require appropriate tools to reduce drudgery and enhance their quality of life. The present study was carried out in the Hisar district of Haryana state with the particular objective of assessing the symbolic adoption of energy conservation equipment by rural women who were willing to acquire knowledge. Four villages (Ludas, Rawalwas Khurd, Siswal, & Neoli Kalan) adopted by College of Home Science under RAWE programme in the past years were selected purposively. From each village 25 rural women were selected purposively, a total of 100 respondents were selected. Symbolic adoption was assessed through asking questions regarding the willingness of respondents to adopt the energy conservation equipment after imparting the knowledge. The findings revealed that the majority of respondents (58.0%) were in the age group of 20-35 years and most were married (87.0%). More than half (58.0%) had nuclear families. About 27.0 percent of the respondents were educated up to 10+2 level. A majority were housewives (64.0%), while 26.0 percent were engaged in farming. Equipment showing the highest symbolic adoption included pressure cookers, LED lights, CFLs and tube lights (mean score = 3.0), improved *chulhas* (2.82), solar bulbs and fans (2.52) and solar inverters (2.51). Despite high willingness, actual adoption after exposure remained low, only 7 respondents adopted LEDs, 5 CFLs, 4 tube lights, 6 improved *chulhas*, 4 pressure cookers and 2 solar bulbs. The results highlight the need for financial support, awareness campaigns and follow-up initiatives to convert symbolic intent into actual adoption and encourage rural women to adopt sustainable energy practices.

Keywords: Symbolic adoption, energy conservation equipment, rural women and Home Science

India's energy consumption has skyrocketed as a result of urbanization, population growth and the expansion of the IT industry. Energy is the primary driver of economic growth and is essential to the long-term viability of modern economies and societies. The long-term availability, accessibility and security of energy supplies will have a substantial impact on future economic growth (Ramesh & Khan, 2013). According to Pachauri and Meyer (2014), electricity and heat production are responsible for 25.0 percent of total global GHG emissions. This emphasizes how crucial and urgent it is to use energy sustainably in order to lower GHG emissions. India is the second most populous country in the world.

The nation has a very high level of energy consumption in all forms. Despite the fact that emerging countries account for 80.0 percent of the world's population, their energy use accounts for just 40.0 percent of overall global consumption. The high levels of energy use in industrialized countries are responsible for their high living standards. Individuals in developed countries consume four to five times as much energy as the global average and nine times as much as people in developing countries (Bureau of Energy Efficiency, 2009).

The majority of rural women suffer not only from economic poverty, but also from information poverty, particularly in terms of enhanced household technologies for better performance as home managers. Numerous areas where women are disadvantaged, including education and information, reproductive health, infrastructures livelihoods, transportation and communications, could be improved by technology. Women's usage of seemingly basic technologies can empower them on several levels, inspiring spheres of change (Malhotra et al, 2009). Technological breakthroughs and their dissemination to rural women can improve women's welfare and empowerment. Low-cost, dependable homestead technologies related to nutrition, health and sanitation, drudgery reduction, post-harvest technologies, etc. can provide a significant leap forward in meeting rural women's practical needs for reducing drudgery, increasing efficiency and improving family health (Choudhary & Solanki, 2018).

The social and environmental aspects of energy use must be taken into account by policymakers in order to successfully encourage

Author Note

¹Meenu, PhD Scholar, Department of Resource Management and Consumer Science, I.C. College of Community Science, Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana

²Yashpal Yadav, PhD Scholar, Department of Farm Machinery and Power Engineering, College of Technology and Engineering Maharana Pratap University of Agriculture & Technology, Udaipur Rajasthan

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Meenu, PhD Scholar, Department of Resource Management and Consumer Science, I.C. College of Community Science, Chaudhary Charan Singh Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar, Haryana
E-mail: meenujakhar1998@gmail.com

rural women to symbolically adopt energy-saving devices. Education campaigns that emphasize the advantages of energy efficiency for households, the community and the environment at large should be part of any strategy. Furthermore, removing financial obstacles through the provision of subsidies or incentives can facilitate rural women's investment in energy-saving technologies. Adopting energy-saving equipment can be viewed as an act of empowerment. Women who use clean energy technologies not only increase the efficiency of their households, but they also gain agency in energy-related decision-making processes.

Objective of the Study

To assess the symbolic adoption of energy conservation equipment by rural women

Method

The study was conducted in Hisar district of Haryana state. Hisar district was purposively selected for the survey work four villages (Ludas, Rawalwas Khurd, Siswal and Neoli Kalan) adopted by College of Home Science under RHWE programme in the past years were purposively selected to study the symbolic adoption regarding energy conservation equipment by rural women.

Participants

25 rural women respondents were selected purposively from each village. Thus a total of 100 respondents were selected as sample respondents for this study.

Measure

The data were collected with the help of a well-structured and pre-tested interview schedule, which comprised of questions about the background profile of respondents and questions regarding willingness of respondents to adopt the energy conservation equipment. Knowledge was imparted to 100 rural respondents (25 from each village) about energy conservation equipment. Knowledge was imparted through print media developed by citing relevant literature. Symbolic adoption was studied after 30 days of imparting knowledge to 100 rural respondents.

Statistical Analysis and Procedure

The data collected were processed, tabulated and analyzed using frequency, percentages and mean score.

Plate 1

Filling Questionnaire during Data Collection

Results and Discussion

Background profile of the respondents: The data highlights that a majority (58.0 %) of the respondents belonged to the age group of 20-35 years, followed by 32.0 percent in the 35-50 years category

and only 10.0 percent were between 50-65 years of age group. A significant proportion of the respondents were married (87.0 %), while 7.0 percent were unmarried and 6.0 percent were widows. According to Ravindra and Kaur (2016), married women, especially those in joint or nuclear families, have a tendency to choose energy appliances when they become aware of the issue through community-based or extension-based initiatives. Regarding caste distribution, 39.0 percent of the respondents belonged to the Scheduled Caste (SC) category, 30.0 percent were from the Backward Class (BC) and 31.0 percent were from the General category. Regarding family structure, 58.0 percent lived in nuclear families and 42.0 percent were part of joint families. This finding aligns with the study of Devi and Rani (2020) which highlighted a gradual shift from joint to nuclear family systems in rural Haryana. Nuclear families were reported to enjoy greater autonomy in decision-making, which may positively influence awareness and adoption behaviour. The majority (57.0 %) had a family size of 5-7 members, 35.0 percent had 2-4 members and only 8.0 percent had larger families with 8-10 members. Most of the respondents had

Table 1

Personal and Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents (N=100)

S.No.	Variables	Category	Percentage
1.	Age (in years)	20-35	58.0
		35-50	32.0
		50-65	10.0
2.	Marital status	Married	87.0
		Unmarried	7.0
		Widow	6.0
3.	Caste	SC	39.0
		BC	30.0
		General	31.0
4.	Family type	Nuclear	58.0
		Joint	42.0
5.	Family size	2-4 members	35.0
		5-7 members	57.0
		8-10 members	8.0
6.	Education of respondents	Illiterate	10.0
		Primary	11.0
		Middle	13.0
		High School	21.0
7.	Occupation of respondent	10+2	27.0
		Graduate and above	18.0
		Govt. service	3.0
		Business	3.0
		Farming	26.0
8.	Monthly income of respondent (Rs.)	Labour	4.0
		Housewife	64.0
		< 25000	71.0
		25001 - 50000	29.0
9.	Main family occupation	Govt. service	11.0
		Private service	24.0
		Farming	28.0
		Labour	20.0
		Business	17.0
10.	Total monthly family income (Rs.)	< 25000	73.0
		25001-50000	22.0
		51001 -75000	5.0

completed 10+2 (27.0 percent), followed by high school education (21.0 %) and graduation or above (18.0 %). Others had education up to middle (13.0 %), primary level (11.0 %), while 10.0 percent were illiterate. Regarding occupation of respondents, data showed that 64.0 percent were housewives, 26.0 percent engaged in farming, 4.0 percent worked as laborers and a small portion were in government service (3.0 percent) or business (3.0 percent). A large proportion of respondents (71.0%) earned less than ₹25,000, while 29.0 percent fell in the ₹25,001-₹50,000 range of monthly income category. The main family occupation was farming for 28.0 percent of the respondents, followed by private service (24.0 %), labour (20.0 %), business (17.0 %) and government service (11.0 %). The total monthly income of most families (73.0%) was less than ₹25,000, followed by 22.0 percent in the ₹25,001-₹50,000 range and only 5.0 percent earning between ₹51,001- ₹75,000.

Table 2 shows the symbolic adoption status of various cooking-related energy-saving devices among rural women. The data reflects their prior ownership, actual adoption after awareness exposure and their expressed willingness to adopt different technologies. None of the respondents had adopted the solar cooker (box type) before or after exposure. However, 41.0 percent of the respondents indicated a willingness to adopt it after being imparted with knowledge. A larger proportion (47.0 %) remained undecided and 12.0 percent were not willing to adopt it. In dish type solar cooker, 30.0 percent respondents were willing to adopt it, while 26.0 percent respondents had not decided and 44.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt it. The mean score was 1.86, indicating a relatively low symbolic inclination most likely due to perceived complexity, maintenance issues or cost barriers. Regarding solar dryer, 32.0 percent of respondents showed willingness to adopt it, 43.0 percent respondents had not decided and 25.0 percent were unwilling. The mean score of 2.07 reflects a fair level of symbolic adoption but also highlights uncertainty, possibly due to lack of familiarity or concerns regarding usability. The improved *chulha* (MDV *chulha*) recorded the highest willingness among those who had not already adopted it. Out of 68 respondents who had not previously owned or purchased

one, 82.3 percent expressed a tendency to adopt it after exposure, with only 17.7 percent uncertain. The mean score of 2.82 indicates high symbolic acceptance, most likely due to its low cost, ease of use, and fuel efficiency in traditional cooking practices.

Figure 1

Personal and Socio-economic Profile of the Respondents

Table 2

Symbolic Adoption of Equipment for Cooking

S. No.	Equipment for cooking	Already owned (adopted) before exposure	Adopted/ purchased after exposure	Willingness to adopt/purchase equipment after imparting knowledge				Mean score	Respondents who have not adopted/purchased before and after exposure
				Willing to adopt	Undecided	Not willing to adopt			
1.	Solar cooker								
a)	Box type	-	-	41(41.0)	47(47.0)	12(12.0)	2.29	n=100	
b)	Dish type	-	-	30(30.0)	26(26.0)	44(44.0)	1.86	n=100	
2.	Solar dryer	-	-	32(32.0)	43(43.0)	25(25.0)	2.07	n=100	
3.	Improved <i>chulha</i> (MDV <i>chulha</i>)	26	6	56(82.3)	12(17.7)	-	2.82	n=68	
4.	Pressure cooker	78	4	18(100.0)	-	-	3.0	n=18	
5.	Pellet stove	-	-	18(18.0)	45(45.0)	37(37.0)	1.81	n=100	

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

Of the 18 respondents who had never owned or purchased one before, all (100.0 percent) expressed a willingness to adopt it after the exposure. The mean score was the highest possible 3.0 indicating

agreed upon symbolic approval. In case of pressure cooker, 4.0 percent respondents had purchased pressure cooker and 18.0 percent respondents were willing to purchase in future (M.S.= 3.0).

Conversely, the pellet stove received the least symbolic acceptance. 18.0 percent of respondents were willing to adopt in future, 45.0 percent respondents were indecisive and 37.0 percent respondents were unwilling (M.S.=1.81). In conclusion, equipment that is already familiar, affordable and viewed as useful such as the pressure cooker and improved *chulha* showed the greatest symbolic

acceptance. Newer or more advanced technology, such as the pellet stove and dish-type solar cooker, encountered increased resistance or uncertainty. These findings highlight the importance of exposure, demonstration and affordability in increasing the symbolic and actual adoption of energy-efficient cooking equipment among rural women.

Table 3*Symbolic Adoption of Equipment for Lighting*

S. No.	Equipment for lighting	Already owned (adopted) before exposure	Adopted/ purchased after exposure	Willingness to adopt/purchase equipment after imparting knowledge				
				Willing to adopt	Undecided	Not willing to adopt	Mean score	Respondents who have not adopted/purchased before and after exposure
1.	Solar lantern	-	-	25(25.0)	53(53.0)	22(22.0)	2.03	n=100
2.	Solar light/ bulb	6	2	55(59.8)	30(32.6)	7(7.6)	2.52	n=92
3.	LED	36	7	57(100.0)	-	-	3.0	n=57
4.	CFL	83	5	12(100.0)	-	-	3.0	n=12
5.	Tube light	71	4	25(100.0)	-	-	3.0	n=25

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

Table 3 shows the symbolic adoption status of various lighting-related energy saving equipment among rural women, based on ownership status prior to exposure, actual adoption after awareness and willingness to adopt the equipment after knowledge transfer. In case of solar lantern, none of the respondents had adopted them before or immediately after the exposure. However, 25.0 percent respondents expressed willingness to adopt it in future, while a majority (53.0%) remained undecided and 22.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt/purchase it. The mean score of 2.03 indicates moderate symbolic acceptance, but the high indecision rate suggests that more demonstrations and user engagement are required to overcome uncertainty and perceived risk. Regarding solar light/bulb, among the 92 respondents who had not adopted or purchased them, 59.8 percent were willing to adopt after exposure. Meanwhile, 32.6 percent remained undecided and only 7.6 percent were unwilling. The mean score was 2.52, reflecting a relatively high symbolic inclination, possibly due to the increasing visibility and practicality of solar lighting in rural areas.

The LED lights had the highest level of symbolic adoption. Among 57 respondents who had never owned or purchased LEDs

previously, all (100.0 %) expressed willingness to adopt the equipment. The mean score reached a high of 3.0, signifying widespread symbolic acceptability. This indicates that LED technology is well known, trusted and linked to long-term cost savings and energy efficiency. Similarly, CFL bulbs also recorded high symbolic adoption among those who had not previously owned or purchased them. All 12 respondents expressed a willingness to adopt CFLs after exposure, with a mean score of 3.0. In case of tube lights, it also showed the high symbolic acceptance among the 25 respondents who had not adopted or purchased them before. All 25 (100.0 %) indicated willingness to adopt, resulting again in a full mean score of 3.0. All things considered, the symbolic adoption of lighting equipment was noticeably higher for well-known, mainstream, and tested technologies like LEDs, CFLs and tube lights, whereas reactions to newer alternatives like solar lanterns and solar bulbs were more mixed. In order to close the gap between symbolic and practical adoption, awareness campaigns, live demonstrations and cost-cutting measures are still necessary. This is especially true for solar-based lighting solutions.

Table 4*Symbolic Adoption of Equipment for Room Cooling*

S. No.	Equipment room cooling	Already owned (adopted) before exposure	Adopted/ purchased after exposure	Willingness to adopt/purchase equipment after imparting knowledge				
				Willing to adopt	Undecided	Not willing to adopt	Mean score	Respondents who have not adopted/purchased before and after exposure
1.	Solar fan	6	2	55(59.8)	30(32.6)	7(7.6)	2.52	n=92
2.	Solar room cooler	-	-	52(52.0)	38(38.0)	10(10.0)	2.42	n=100

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

In Table 4, regarding solar fan, only 6 respondents' reported prior ownership, while 2 adopted the equipment following exposure. Among the remaining 92 respondents who neither owned nor adopted

the solar fan, 59.8 percent expressed a willingness to adopt, 32.6 percent remained undecided and only 7.6 percent were not willing to adopt. The mean score of 2.52 indicates a relatively strong symbolic

acceptance of solar fans. This demonstrates a rising awareness of their utility, particularly in rural areas with frequent power outages, yet uncertainty among a considerable number suggests continuing concerns about performance, pricing or availability. For the solar room cooler, none of the respondents had adopted the equipment either before or after the exposure. However, symbolic adoption was

moderately positive with 52.0 percent expressing willingness to adopt after knowledge dissemination. Meanwhile, 38.0 percent remained undecided and 10.0 percent were not willing to adopt. The mean score of 2.42 reflects a fair degree of symbolic acceptance, although the large number of undecided respondents points to limited familiarity or higher cost perceptions that may hinder actual adoption.

Table 5*Symbolic Adoption of Equipment for Recreation*

S. No.	Equipment for recreation	Already owned (adopted) before exposure	Adopted/ purchased after exposure	Willingness to adopt/purchase equipment after imparting knowledge				
				Willing to adopt	Undecided	Not willing to adopt	Mean score	Respondents who have not adopted/purchased before and after exposure
1.	Solar TV	-	-	48(48.0)	37(37.0)	15(15.0)	2.33	n=100
2.	Solar radio/ transistor	-	-	35(35.0)	40(40.0)	25(25.0)	2.10	n=100

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

Table 5 depicts the symbolic adoption of solar-powered recreational equipment by rural women following exposure to energy conservation awareness. The data shows that 48.0 percent respondents were willing to adopt solar TV, 37.0 percent respondents had not decided and 15.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt (M.S.=2.33). Out of 100 respondents 35.0 percent respondents

were willing to adopt solar radio/transistor in future, 40.0 percent respondents had not decided and 25.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt (M.S.= 2.10). Overall, the data indicates a fair level of symbolic acceptance of solar-powered recreational equipment among rural women.

Table 6*Symbolic Adoption of Miscellaneous Equipment*

S. No.	Miscellaneous equipment	Already owned (adopted) before exposure	Adopted/ purchased after exposure	Willingness to adopt/purchase equipment after imparting knowledge				
				Willing to adopt	Undecided	Not willing to adopt	Mean score	Respondents who have not adopted/purchased before and after exposure
1.	Solar water heater/geyser	-	-	18(18.0)	30(30.0)	52(52.0)	1.66	n=100
2.	Solar tube well	-	-	14(14.0)	25(25.0)	61(61.0)	1.53	n=100
3.	Solar inverter	8	-	55(59.8)	29(31.5)	8(8.70)	2.51	n=92

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

Table 6 outlines the symbolic adoption pattern of various miscellaneous energy-efficient devices among rural women, assessed after they were exposed to knowledge regarding energy conservation. In case of solar water heater/ geyser, only 18.0 percent

respondents showed willingness to adopt in symbolically, whereas 30.0 percent remained undecided and 52.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt. The mean score of 1.66, the second lowest in the category, indicates low symbolic acceptance, possibly due to

Table 7*Symbolic adoption of fuel saving vehicles*

S. No.	Miscellaneous equipment	Already owned (adopted) before exposure	Adopted/ purchased after exposure	Willingness to adopt/purchase equipment after imparting knowledge				
				Willing to adopt	Undecided	Not willing to adopt	Mean score	Respondents who have not adopted/purchased before and after exposure
1.	CNG vehicle	-	-	12(12.0)	40(40.0)	48(48.0)	1.64	n=100
2.	Electric/ battery operated scooty	6	-	15(16.0)	56(59.5)	23(24.5)	1.91	n=94
3.	Electric/ battery operated rickshaw	-	-	20(20.0)	30(30.0)	50(50.0)	1.70	n=100

Note. (Figures in parentheses indicate percentages)

perceived high cost, limited water availability or climatic unsuitability in certain regions. Regarding solar tube well, of the 100 respondents, 14.0 percent respondents were willing to adopt in future, 25.0 percent respondents had not decided and a significant 61.0 percent respondents expressed unwillingness. The mean score was only 1.53, the lowest among all items assessed in this category, indicating lack of feasibility. In contrast, the solar inverter showed a relatively high symbolic adoption. 59.8 percent were symbolically willing to adopt it after gaining knowledge, 31.5 percent had not decided and 8.70 percent respondents were unwilling to adopt. The mean score of 2.51 suggests strong symbolic acceptance, likely due to the immediate and visible utility of inverters in managing household power backups.

Table 7 presents the symbolic adoption status of fuel saving vehicles among rural respondents.

In case of CNG vehicle, 12.0 percent respondents expressed a willingness to adopt symbolically, while 40.0 percent had not decided and 48.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt. The mean score of 1.64 indicates a low level of symbolic acceptance, possibly due to limited availability of CNG refueling infrastructure in rural areas or higher upfront costs. Regarding electric/battery operated scooty, 6 respondents had already adopted this vehicle. Among the remaining 94, 16.0 percent showed willingness to adopt, 59.5 percent had not decided and 24.5 percent respondents were not willing to adopt. With a mean score of 1.91, it reflects moderate symbolic interest, likely influenced by ease of use, low maintenance and growing visibility of such vehicles in semi-urban and peri-urban areas.

Regarding electric/battery operated rickshaw, 20.0 percent respondents were willing to adopt in future, 30.0 percent had not decided and 50.0 percent respondents were not willing to adopt (M.S.= 1.70). Overall, there was little symbolic adoption of fuel-efficient vehicles, indicating that while the financial and environmental advantages are clear, real adoption interest is still limited. This suggests that in order to encourage sustainable transport options in rural areas, awareness campaigns, policy support and incentive programs are required.

Summary and Conclusion

The present study concluded that a majority of the respondents (58.0%) belonged to the age group of 20-35 years, 87.0 percent were married and most were from the Scheduled Caste category (39.0%). More than half (58.0 percent) lived in nuclear families and 57.0

percent had a family size of 5-7 members. 27.0 percent of the respondents were educated up to 10+2 level. A majority were housewives (64.0%), 26.0 percent were engaged in farming and 71.0 percent respondents' monthly income was less than ₹ 25,000. Regarding family occupation, most were involved in farming (28.0%) and 73.0 percent respondents had a total monthly family income of less than ₹ 25,000. The study found that symbolic adoption (willingness to adopt) of energy conservation equipment was highest for pressure cookers, LEDs, CFLs, and tube lights (mean score = 3.0), followed by improved chulhas (mean = 2.82), solar bulbs & fans (2.52) and solar inverters (2.51). Lower symbolic adoption was observed for solar tube wells (1.53), solar geysers (1.66), CNG vehicles (1.64), battery-operated rickshaws (1.70), and pellet stoves (1.81). However, actual adoption or purchase after exposure remained limited, only 7 respondents adopted LEDs, 5 adopted CFLs, 4 adopted tube lights, 2 adopted solar bulbs, 6 adopted improved chulhas and 4 adopted pressure cookers. These findings indicate a positive shift in awareness and willingness to adopt energy-efficient technologies among rural women after exposure, yet financial and infrastructural barriers continue to hinder actual adoption. Therefore, policy-level support such as subsidies, better accessibility and follow-up interventions are recommended to convert symbolic adoption into practical usage.

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